

From Critique to Action in Design Practice

Sonja Rattay

University of Copenhagen

Criticism for digital technologies continues to call out the consequences of short-sighted technical implementations. Academic critique and public concern point out problems and demand better, more just design practices. These calls, however, often emphasize undeniably important but abstract ideas and principles of justice that are difficult to translate to practice. At the same time, in design itself as a commercial endeavour, discussions around the political impact of the design of digital technology are stuck on attempts to solve these challenges through commercialised approaches such as new sustainability themed tool kits or diversity themed card decks, without wanting to significantly change the established ways of working.

I am part of the European research network DCODE, which aims to re-think design to reconcile human values and algorithmic logic with sustainable social, economic and political models for inclusive, sustainable, digital futures. My project investigates not just what these inclusive and just futures might look like but also how we might get there. Before turning to research to investigate actionable ways of integrating politically sensitive and responsible practices in design, I encountered the frustrating limitations that come with the responsibilities of running a company and committing to a service provider relationship as provided through design consulting. As a professional designer, co-founder of a design studio and former head of design, discussions around ethical responsibility of designers and developers have been a part of my everyday working life, however framed and limited by the demands of project work reality such as time and resource scarcity, client and stakeholder interests, and economic feasibility. Realising that, as a professional designer, it is difficult to change a system upon which my livelihood depends, I decided to move to academia. As part of the DCODE project, I am now researching the dynamics through which designers partake and reinforce power imbalances and systemic injustices from a position of professional interest, but also lived experience and pragmatic understanding of the realities of commercial design work, which motivates me to ensure that my theoretical and empirical work has real consequences and can lead to relevant change, which I haven't seen in the last years.

2016 was the year the first bigger tech backlash news stories broke. In that summer, I facilitated a strategy focused workshop series to create scenarios of future smart home systems for a big. For 10 days straight, we had discussed, imagined, investigated, speculated and ideated around the future connected home

appliances, the notion people have of their private spaces and the potentials and challenges it would bring for new products and services in the next decade. Feeling inspired and confident in having delivered a great job I relived the experience by telling a colleague about it in detail, and in passing they mentioned an article they had read about the potential dangers of camera equipped robot vacuum cleaners, which map their owners' homes, and female voiced smart assistants positioned as servants. They forwarded me the article. The next day, I questioned more than half of the work we had done in the prior 10 days. Here it was, a clear description and listing of questionable features we had discussed, along with the potential dangers, laid out in all its creepiness. All ignored while being in the creative glowy haze of imagining a completely autonomous, always cozy, always clean and ready-for-you home. There are plenty of such examples that highlight that technological progress left unattended does not by itself provide better solutions for all parts of society, and negatively affects already vulnerable groups and individual [5]. As a result, there are increasing calls for responsible technologies designed ethically. The notion however of what constitutes ethical design of systems and technology is a fuzzy one [2]. That moment of reckoning from five years ago stays with me, because the project encapsulated so many points of tension around what was being discussed or dismissed in terms of ethical considerations, deemed irrelevant or "not our responsibility" as designers.

While learning more helps to critically reflect, it is not necessarily the amount of criticism that is lacking, but the options to create change and affect practice in my field. Which leads me to my current research work on design practices for ethics in action. Aiming to rethink methods and practices that enable designers to take social justice aspects into account, I am challenging how designers think about their processes, politics and position in the industry. However, making these politics an active part of the design process is a frustratingly slow endeavor, facing challenges at various points. Questions that came up during the smart home project, such as ownership of responsibility, scope of consequences to be considered and such, make people uncomfortable and are not necessarily the fabric good design stories are made of. They clash with the commercialized and commodified nature of many design tool-kits, frameworks and methods, which promise to enable "more ethical" design with ease by fixing small aspects and components of established design tools (such as personas or how might we's) without questioning deeply embedded power structures they are actually masking [8] [6] [7]. Keeping notions of justice concrete in simplified design tools is impossible, as they turn specific questions of justice into abstracted principles that become opaque in their generality [4].

Additionally, design teams tend to generally be rather non-diverse, reinforcing design decisions to be made over and over again from a limited, and often privileged, viewpoint, while being masked as the

neutral result of an unbiased process. Seeing the act of designing as a political activity tied to individual experiences of justice and injustices, and thus taking a politically situated stance as a designer clashes with what many designers see as their identity - an open-minded and unbiased problem solver, a neutral facilitator. Almost as if the saying “good design is unnoticeable” transfers to the designer themselves. But in order to make a dent, to take action, a person must be noticeable, and infusing political themes into commercial design work is activism. It requires uncomfortable questions to be asked to people who might not yet be open to them, and collective shifts in the imaginaries that shape the act of designing. The judgment calls in terms of which anticipatory changes are to be made is a political one, as it defines which aspects of the existing world ought to be changed or left alone [1]. Through their work, designers manifest imaginaries of our everyday life, and we need to challenge the existing imaginaries and find ways to channel the resulting changes into research and design practice [3].

I want to use my research to facilitate that type of change, but endeavors such as this require community and collaboration. In this workshop I hope to find a community that can benefit from my experiences as well research, and within which I can learn to further develop my understandings and approaches to social justice work within HCI, as well as find ways to develop my research into activist work, which extends beyond the academic frame and finds a foot hold in the real and acute situations it is needed in.

References

- [1] Bardzell, S. 2010. Feminist HCI: taking stock and outlining an agenda for design. *Proceedings of the 28th international conference on Human factors in computing systems - CHI '10* (Atlanta, Georgia, USA, 2010), 1301.
- [2] Frauenberger, C. et al. 2017. In-Action Ethics. *Interacting with Computers*. 29, 2 (Mar. 2017), 220–236. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1093/iwc/iww024>.
- [3] Jasanoff, S. 2015. One. *Future Imperfect: Science, Technology, and the Imaginations of Modernity*. *One. Future Imperfect: Science, Technology, and the Imaginations of Modernity*. University of Chicago Press. 1–33.
- [4] Manders-Huits, N. 2011. What Values in Design? The Challenge of Incorporating Moral Values into Design. *Science and Engineering Ethics*. 17, 2 (Jun. 2011), 271–287. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-010-9198-2>.
- [5] O’Neil, C. 2016. *Weapons of Math Destruction: How Big Data Increases Inequality and Threatens Democracy*. Crown.
- [6] Phan, T. et al. 2021. Economies of Virtue: The Circulation of ‘Ethics’ in Big Tech. *Science as Culture*. (Nov. 2021).
- [7] The most popular design thinking strategy is BS: 2021. <https://www.fastcompany.com/90649969/the-most-popular-design-thinking-strategy-is-bs>. Accessed: 2022-03-07.
- [8] UX design has a dirty secret: 2021. <https://www.fastcompany.com/90686473/ux-design-has-a-dirty-secret>. Accessed: 2022-02-02.